

PHYSIOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF PAIN SYNDROME IN INFANTS

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Annotation: Pain is an unpleasant sensory—emotional state associated with true or potential tissue damage.

Pain syndrome in newborns is a problem for many doctors, since newborns cannot express their pain in words.

That is why the ability of a doctor to correctly interpret clinical data plays an important role in the recognition and assessment of pain syndrome in a newborn.

Keywords: pain, infant, pain syndrome, adrenal glands, hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal system, mediator.

The problem of pain is associated with many aspects - anatomical, physiological, psychological, pharmacological, legal, social aspects. This problem is the problem of all specialists surgeons, anesthesiologists, neurologists.

The bark of the Cerebral Hemispheres controls conditional-reflective activity, the severity of pain, its continuation, its elimination.

Clinicians divide pathological pain into two groups. The first is a pathological process in the internal organs, abdominal and chest cavities. The second group is pain in the skin, subcutaneous cartilage, muscles, bones and joints.

There are views on pain and a number of unresolved problems aimed at solving this problem. The problem of pain remains a problem of such areas of science as medicine, philosophy, ethics. The International Association for the Study of Pain - IASP describes pain as "an unpleasant sensory and emotional irritation caused by tissue damage. The hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal system operates from

the second trimester of fetal life. At 30 weeks of gestation, fetal cortisol levels are 5-10 mg/ ml, at 36 weeks -20 mg/ ml, 45 mg/ ml before the birth, when the baby is born, this indicator increases and amounts to of 200 mg/ ml. A sharp increase in this indicator ensures the adaptation of the baby to external influences. The screening level of cortisol in infants is 414-138 nmol/l (starting from 29 weeks of gestation). Fetal steroidogenesis changes during fetal development and delivery, when exposed to placental enzymes, when exposed to cytokines and free oxygen radical. Premature detachment of the placenta, childbirth, intrauterine infection sharply affect the amount of steroids in the blood of the navel. Many scientists recommend determining the amount of cortisol in the saliva, since 90% of cortisol is excreted with special proteins, 7% is albumin, 3% is a biological active substance. Due to painful procedures, the amount of cortisol increases. In the treatment of physiological disorders that are caused by hyperproduction of cortisol, but cannot cope with stress disorder, pain. High levels of cortisol contribute to the development of metabolic syndrome, cognitive impairment. Many authors have argued that there is a gender difference in relation to the pain effect, that is, in the somatosensory zone of the cranial cortex relative to the pain effect, oxygenation is higher in boys. Serotonin and gamma-aminobutyric acid are active in the prenatal period and play an important role in reducing pain modulation.

Hormones secreted into the blood by the internal secretion glands change the internal motility, composition, biological properties of the body. The endocrine glands react instantly to pain and thus increase or decrease the secretion of hormones. Constant impulses from the brain and spinal cord, cortex, subcortical structures, and autonomic nervous system ensure the constant nature of pain.

Mediators (acetylcholine, norepinephrine, histamine), accumulating in the nerve endings in the skin, do not split under the influence of tissue enzymes, but pass into the blood, organs, and tissue fluid stimulate or inhibit their activity. In response to pain, all internal secretion glands exert their influence: the adrenal glands, pituitary gland, thyroid gland, pancreas. The brain layer of the adrenal

glands secretes the hormone- adrenaline, which is universal.. Adrenaline-secreting cells are located in the inner part o of the adrenal gland. Adrenaline increases the activity of the sympathetic nervous system, the activity of all organs.

Adrenaline is detected in venous blood in the pain zone. As a result of pain, the activity of the adrenal medulla increases and a large amount of adrenaline is released into the blood.

As a result of severe pain, hormonal and mediator functions are further increased. First of all, the heart is supplied with adrenaline, while the consumption of norepinephrine is doubled. If the pain continues to strain, the sympatho-adrenal system weakens, the adrenaline content in the heart decreases, and the secretion of norepinephrine by nerve endings slows down. Adrenaline in the bloodstream is not absorbed by the heart, while deep changes occur in the brain. As a result of the pain syndrome, the level of norepinephrine in the hypothalamus decreases. Norepinephrine is released from the bound state and acts on the adrenergic elements of the reticular formation.

Adrenaline accumulates in the brain and passes through the blood-brain barrier, spreading from the blood to the hypothalamus, and then to other parts of the brain.

Several experiments have shown that when an electric current is applied to a nerve, the production of adrenaline and norepinephrine by sympathetic nerves in adrenal cells increases. The content of various catecholamines — adrenaline, norepinephrine, dopamine - in the blood varies. It will depend on the nature, strength and duration of external influence. As a result of the strong pain effect, the acuity of the hormones of the adrenal gland is greater in order to maintain the normal functioning of the body. There are more than 40 hormones known as corticosteroids that control the metabolism of proteins, fats, carbohydrates, minerals entering the body. According to its structure and functional properties, the cortical layer of the adrenal glands is divided into three zones: the glomerular one produces mineralocorticoids that control the exchange of potassium and sodium,

the bundle zone -glucocorticoids that control the exchange of carbohydrates, and in the mesh zone-sex hormones.

All the endocrine glands are located at the base of the pituitary gland, which regulates the activity of all the endocrine glands, consisting of the anterior and posterior sections, which, due to their location, secrete hormones into the blood and cerebrospinal fluid. Adrenocorticotrophic hormone controls the secretion of corticosteroids, stimulates the secretion; thyroid—stimulating hormone affects the function of the thyroid gland, gonadotropin - on the activity of the gonads [9,10].

In the pituitary anterior compartment, growth hormone is produced, in the middle compartment—a hormone that promotes the aging of pigment production, in the posterior compartment-vasopressin, which affects blood pressure, and oxytocin, which promotes uterine tightness. In the anterior pituitary gland, growth hormone is produced, in the middle section—a hormone responsible for aging and pigment production, in the posterior section - vasopressin, which affects blood pressure, and oxytocin, which promotes uterine contraction.

As a result of pain, the secretion of pituitary hormones is disrupted. This is due to an increase in the amount of hormones in the blood and in the cerebrospinal fluid, which changes the content of the composition of the cerebrospinal fluid and disrupts metabolism in the cells of the brain and spinal cord tissue. Thyroxine, like adrenaline, stimulates the activity of the sympathetic nervous system. As a result of the painful effect, the activity of the thyroid gland is activated. The hormone thyroxine is released into the blood, which enhances cardiac activity, accelerates metabolism. The intensity and nature of the pain are related to the functioning of the thyroid gland, which regulates potassium metabolism in the body. In what order hormones secreted by the endocrine glands are released during pain. It is worth saying that initially the activity of the brain and spinal cord makes up for each other's work, strengthens or weakens. In the early stages of pain, adrenaline and thyroxine are produced, which stimulate the activity of the brain and spinal cord, followed by mediators, metabolites and hormones that dull the pain. The

hormone of the pancreas - insulin, which increases the activity of the parasympathetic nervous system, is released during prolonged pain. Insulin enhances the function of the parasympathetic nervous system by lowering blood sugar levels. As a result of exposure to prolonged pain, dominant foci of inflammation are formed in various structures of the nervous system, changes in the functioning of organs and physiological systems appear separately. With acute pain, breathing becomes faster and deeper, sweat secretion increases, gastric juice secretion decreases, digestion of food is inhibited, the composition and nature of blood changes, the number of red blood cells and leukocytes. What effect leads to an increase in the activity of the pituitary gland as a result, the release of adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) increases, which stimulates the activity of the cortical layer of the adrenal glands, resulting in a large amount of corticosteroids entering the blood. The structure and functions of all types of corticosteroids create excellent conditions for the development of stress. As a result of a violation of hormone secretion, an adaptation cycle is disrupted. Pain stress is a complex accompanied by fear. The first stage of stress is an anxiety reaction, which Selye describes as a period of adaptation during which the body resists with all its might in the second stage, which Selye describes as the "resistance stage". It is at this stage that corticosteroids begin to be intensively produced in the cortical layer of the adrenal glands to protect the body from damage. If the stressor continues to attack, the third stage of stress begins. As the secretion of hormones of the adrenal cortex is disrupted, adaptive diseases arise as a result. Since the changes caused by severe stress were known as the village general adaptation syndrome. Due to stress (pain, illness, physical exertion, emotional disorder), complex nervous mechanisms are triggered. The cerebral cortex transmits signals to the subcortical structures and hypothalamus about the expected risk. In any situation, stressful effects that pose a health risk are possible, so the hypothalamus triggers protective mechanisms. The amount of adrenaline and norepinephrine in the body and tissues increases, they cause stress reactions called

"disaster hormones". The accumulation of norepinephrine ensures the adaptation of the body to stress factors, side effects [5,7].

Complex special compounds in special cells that are produced in the hypothalamus are releasing, nerve fibers that connect the hypothalamus to the pituitary gland, and releasing provide synthesis of adrenocorticotrophic hormone in the pituitary gland. Let's say an injured child has a broken arm due to an accident. as a result, the hormone adrenaline is released into the blood, which after a while passes through the hemato-encephalic barrier, affecting the posterior parts of the hypothalamus, triggering them. These effects reach the cells that produce releasing factors, . As a result of nervous and humoral signals, adrenocorticotrophic hormone is released into the blood, resulting in the release of corticosteroids that accumulate in the blood. In acute, unbearable pain, severe stress, traumatic brain injury, severe cooling, or overheating leads to increased conduction through the hemato-encephalic barrier, which further increases the flow of catecholamines to the brain. As soon as corticosteroids accumulate in the blood in extremely large quantities, the law of the reverse effect is triggered. As a result, corticosteroids that have passed through the blood-brain barrier enter the cerebrospinal fluid and cerebrospinal fluid, stopping the release of adrenocorticotrophic hormone. Sometimes corticosteroids do not pass through the blood-brain barrier and bind to proteins in the blood, often transcortin. In this case, the hypothalamus cannot send an inhibitory signal to stop the production of adrenocorticotrophic hormone without receiving the necessary information

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